

Mechanics-guided Deterministic 3D Assembly with Biomedical Applications

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Abstract

Complex, three dimensional (3D) structures in biology (e.g. cytoskeletal webs, neural circuits, vasculature networks) form naturally to provide essential functions in even the most basic forms of life. Compelling opportunities exist for analogous 3D architectures in man-made devices, but design options are constrained by existing capabilities in materials growth and assembly. We report routes to previously inaccessible classes of 3D constructs in advanced materials, including device-grade silicon. The approach involves geometric transformation of 2D micro/nanostructures into extended 3D layouts by compressive buckling. It applies not only to a broad set of materials (e.g., semiconductor, polymer and metal), but also to a wide range of length scales (e.g., from 100 nm to 30 mm). To increase the accessible topologies, we proposed a set of ideas for a form of kirigami/origami that allows precise, buckling-driven assembly of 3D mesostructures from 2D micro/nanomembranes with strategically designed geometries and patterns of cuts/creases. The versatile capabilities of this assembly approach allow transformation of virtually any type of existing 2D microsystem technology into a 3D configuration, providing unusual design options in the development of fundamentally new kinds of devices. Demonstrative biomedical devices adopt open mesh, 3D interconnect networks of helical microcoils to offer exceptional low-modulus, elastic mechanics, in compact geometries, with state-of-the-art active components. These devices can enable uniform, omnidirectional stretchability and wireless, multimodal capabilities in physiological health monitoring.